

control the disease economically.

For optimum expression of genetic resistance or susceptibility to BS under natural disease pressure, MM and EM

varieties are sown on or after 1 and 20 Jul, respectively. For NBLs, however, sowing is delayed another 15 to 20 d. EM varieties that escape NBLs when

raooneed face maximum disease pressure and score 0 to 9. LM varieties get sufficient disease pressure even under TS situations. □

Control of rice bacterial blight (BB) by nickel nitrate

A. Chandrasekaran and P. Vidhyasekaran, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

We screened several chemicals to control rice BB. Rice variety IR20 was grown in the field Sep-Dec 1987. Chemicals at 3 concentrations were sprayed at the boot leaf stage, with 3 replications of 10 plants each for each treatment. The top 3 leaves were clip inoculated 24 h after spraying with a virulent isolate of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* at 10^8 colony-forming units/ml. Disease intensity was scored on 25 randomly selected leaves 20 d after inoculation and % leaf area affected was calculated (see table).

Nickel nitrate at 10^{-2} M effectively controlled the disease. No other chemical was effective. Nickel nitrate at 10^{-2} M to control BB was verified in 2 more independent tests in the greenhouse. □

Effect of different chemicals in inducing resistance to rice BB. Aduthurai, India, 1987.

Chemical	Concentration	Disease intensity	
		Grade value	Leaf area affected (%)
Nickel nitrate	10^{-2} M	1.8	3
	10^{-3} M	5.8	35
	10^{-4} M	6.5	44
Sodium fluoride	10^{-2} M	5.7	34
	10^{-3} M	7.4	60
	10^{-4} M	7.3	58
Calcium sulfate	0.2%	7.2	55
	0.5%	6.8	48
	1.0%	6.0	38
Magnesium sulfate	0.2%	5.8	35
	0.5%	6.8	48
	1.0%	6.2	40
Copper sulfate	0.2%	5.9	36
	0.5%	5.3	29
	1.0%	6.2	40
Ferrous sulfate	0.2%	5.9	36
	0.5%	6.8	48
	1.0%	6.3	41
Zinc sulfate	0.2%	6.3	41
	0.5%	7.0	50
	1.0%	7.7	68
Ammonium molybdate	10 ppm	6.3	41
	50 ppm	6.9	49
	100 ppm	7.0	50
Control		7.5	62
LSD (P=0.05)		1.3	2

Insect management

Brown planthopper (BPH) outbreak in Kanchana Buri Province, Thailand

C. Sindhusake, P. Vungsilabutr, and V. Yaklai, Rice Entomology Research Group, Entomology and Zoology Division, Department of Agriculture, Bangkokhen, Bangkok 10900, Thailand

BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) has been a major insect pest of rice in the Central Plain of Thailand since 1973 dry season (DS), but there was no record of serious outbreaks in Yanchana Buri. In April 1988 DS under high temperatures (av

> 35 °C) at Kaosamsibhap Village, Tamaka District, BPH infestation occurred on about 240 ha with continuous irrigation and water standing in the fields.

It caused typical hopperburn symptoms on about 12.8 ha of rice variety RD7 (C4-63/GR88/ / Sigadis). The remaining area, planted to resistant variety RD23 (RD7/IR32//RDI), was not affected.

Double the recommended N (160 kg/ ha) had been applied as topdressing fertilizer at 40 d after sowing (DAS). Farmers sprayed monocrotophos 2-3 times to control rice thrips, leaf folder, and stem borers.

It is likely that these insecticide applications also caused the BPH outbreak. BPH populations sampled in

untreated fields exceeded 100 hoppers/ hill 83 DAS. Those populations probably came from fields with BPH resurgence. Populations of natural enemies of BPH (mirid bug and wolf spider) also were abundant. □

Chemical control of thrips and gall midge (GM) in rainfed lowland rice

S. K. Panda and N. Shi, Regional Research Station, Orissa University of Agriculture and Technology, Chiplima, Sambabur, Orissa, India

We evaluated insecticides against GM *Orseolia oryzae* during 1988 wet season

in a randomized block design with four replications. Jaya rice seedlings (34-d-old) were planted in 20-m² plots at 20- × 15-cm spacing. Granular insecticides were applied as basal; emulsifiable insecticides were sprayed as needed.

Because of an unusual dry spell, thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* damage occurred at initial tillering; GM was significant only at maximum tillering. Carbofuran as basal alone or with quinalphos spray gave excellent protection against thrips, but not against GM (see table). This may be because the healthier plants in carbofuran-treated plots were more vulnerable to GM than the plants damaged by thrips.

Granular quinalphos treatment produced the highest yield. Spray application of quinalphos was best for GM control. □

Effect of insecticide on GM in rainfed lowland rice in Sambalpur, Orissa, India.

Treatment	Rate (kg ai/ha)	Thrips damage ^a at 25 DT	Silvershoot ^b (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Carbofuran 3 G basal	1.0	0.0	32.8 (34.8)	2.7
Quinalphos 5 G basal	1.0	2.0	13.1 (21.0)	3.3
Quinalphos 25 EC spray at 25 DT	0.5	4.0	3.5 (10.6)	2.9
Monocrotophos 40 EC spray at 25 DT	0.5	3.5	7.1 (15.4)	2.9
Carbofuran 3 G basal + quinalphos 25 EC spray at 25 DT	1.0 + 0.5	0.0	33.6 (35.3)	2.8
Quinalphos 5 G basal + monocrotophos 40 EC spray at 25 DT	1.0 + 0.5	1.5	12.7 (20.5)	3.1
Control		4.0	9.1 (16.6)	2.8
LSD (0.05)		—	7.3	ns

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice. ^bFigures inside parentheses are transformed values.

Effect of sequential neem treatment on green leafhopper (GLH), rice tungro virus (RTV) infection, and predatory mirid and spiders in rice

A. A. Kareem, R. C. Saxena, and M. T. Malayba, Entomology Department, IRRI

In 1987 wet season, we tested a package of neem seed kernel extract (NSKE) treatments on IR42 rice.

The package involved soaking seeds in a 10% NSKE solution, dipping of seedling roots for 12 h in a 5% NSKE

solution, and spraying a 4% NSKE solution emulsified with 1% Teepol at 150 liters/ha 6 times at 10-d intervals from 5 d after transplanting (DT). The neem package was compared with monocrotophos sprayed at 0.75 kg ai/ha. Plot size was 50 m²; each treatment had 7 replications. Field populations of GLH, RTV, and predatory mirid and spiders were sampled visually at 10-d intervals from 8 DT; RTV incidence was recorded 25, 45, and 65 DT.

GLH populations in all treated plots were significantly lower than in untreated plots at 28 DT (Fig. 1). However, predatory mirid and spider populations also were significantly lower in insecticide-treated plots than in neem-treated plots 48 DT. RTV infections in treated plots were not significantly different (Fig. 2). □

Leafhopper nymphs, adults, and predators (no.)/20 hills

1. GLH (a) and predatory mirid and spider populations (b) recovered from 8 to 48 DT on neem- or insecticide-treated plots, IRRI, 1987 wet season. Av of 7 replications. Lines with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

RTV infection (%)

2. Percent RTV infection on plots treated with neem or insecticide, IRRI, 1987 wet season. Av of 7 replications. Bars with a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Storing dry *Beauveria bassiana* mycelium

M. C. Rombach, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research; R. M. Aguda, Entomology Department, IRRI; and D. W. Roberts, Boyce Thompson Institute for Plant Research, Tower Road, Ithaca, NY 14853, USA

The insect fungi (Deuteromycotina: Hyphomycetes) that commonly infect rice insects such as brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) can be isolated on artificial media and mass-produced. Mycelium and conidia of the fungi conventionally are produced by solid fermentation (mycelium growth and sporulation occur on solid substrates) or by diphasic fermentation